

Prevalent Misconception: The Discipline Can Do Its Work Without Naming and Analyzing Palestine and Anti-Palestinian Racism

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The anguish before, during, and after October 7, 2023, has been horrendous. The violence, destruction and death tolls of Palestinians in Gaza still mount. By January 2024, the interim ruling of the International Court of Justice, based on the case brought against Israel by South Africa, underscored that the situation in Gaza was so grave it was plausible to speak of genocide (International Court of Justice 2024). We desperately need to talk about the ideas, actions and structures of power that fuel dehumanizing in-group and out-group constructions. Yet, a central misconception running through the academy in the United States, Canada, and elsewhere, is that political scientists can do their job, and students can learn, without naming or analyzing Palestine and anti-Palestinian racism.

In the English-speaking world negative depictions and stereotypes of Arabs, and Palestinians in particular, are prevalent in media accounts and popular culture (Shaheen 2001; 2008; Abu-Laban 2023). Moreover, evidence of silencing of Palestinian history and the current context and claims of Palestinians abounds. It would be a serious mistake to see this silencing as being confined to the current moment. For decades there has been legitimation of a culture of active repression

on university campuses that has worked to restrict student organizing, limit free expression, and implicitly or explicitly threaten academic freedom when it comes to Palestine (Landy, Lentin, and McCarthy 2020; Abu-Laban and Bakan 2020).

Silencing and erasure are actually core features of anti-Palestinian racism which has been described by the Arab Canadian Lawyers Association as follows:

Anti-Palestinian racism is a form of anti-Arab racism that silences, excludes, erases, stereotypes, defames or dehumanizes Palestinians or their narratives. Anti-Palestinian racism takes various forms including: denying the Nakba and justifying violence against Palestinians; failing to acknowledge Palestinians as an Indigenous people with a collective identity, belonging and rights in relation to occupied and historic Palestine; erasing the human rights and equal dignity and worth of Palestinians; excluding or pressuring others to exclude Palestinian perspectives, Palestinians and their allies; defaming Palestinians and their allies with slander such as being inherently antisemitic, a terrorist threat/sympathizer or opposed to democratic values (Arab Canadian Lawyers Association 2022, 14).

The main difference since October 2023 is that the silencing over Palestine has become obvious, practically everywhere, all at once. Concerted attacks on universities, university professors, academic freedom and free speech threaten core values of the Western academy. Such attacks also raise alarm bells at the highest levels internationally, including the UN where experts have expressed concerns that charges of antisemitism are being used to shut down legitimate discussion (United Nations, 2023). Antisemitism is real and needs to be opposed. But antisemitism cannot be equated with criticism of Israel's policies or the defence of Palestinian human rights.

As it stands, in the heightened climate academics face today, self-censorship is normalized. This accounts for a November 2023 survey of American-based specialists of the Middle East in political science and related fields showing fully 82% of respondents engaged in self-censorship in professional discussions of Israel/Palestine. Of those engaging in self-censorship the majority (81%) did so in relation to criticism of Israel, with decidedly fewer holding back criticism of Palestinians (11%) or the United States (2%) (Lynch and Telhami 2023). Marc Lynch and Shibley Telhami further discuss the report in the introduction of this newsletter.

When even Middle East specialists self-censor, it is not surprising that some non-specialists may actively discourage or even prohibit classroom discussion of current events in Israel and Gaza. On the other side, there are still others who may welcome discussion but seek to achieve a 'balance' by confining discussion to 'the conflict' a word that tends to convey two equal and homogeneous sides. 'The conflict' descriptor often elides analytical clarity when it comes to considerations that are central orienting concepts of political

science: states and power relations.

Political scientists need to crack through the epistemology of ignorance that renders the racism directed at Palestinians—whether under occupation, in Israel, or in the diaspora—somehow unknowable (Mills, 1997; Abu-Laban and Bakan, 2020; Bakan and Abu-Laban, 2021). It can only be done by naming and analyzing Palestine, as well as taking serious account of anti-Palestinian racism and the state structures and processes through which it is expressed. Naming and analyzing Palestine and anti-Palestinian racism can also serve as a basis for refusing to be complicit in this form of racism, as well as a basis for analyzing and challenging all forms of racism, including antisemitism. ♦

References

- Abu-Laban, Yasmeeen. 2023. "Edward Said and the Politics of Race." In Maurice Labelle (ed.). *The Boomerang Effect of Decolonization: Post-Orientalism and the Politics of Difference*, 103-119. Montreal and Kingston: McGill-Queen's University Press.
- Abu-Laban, Yasmeeen and Abigail B. Bakan. 2020. *Israel, Palestine and the Politics of Race: Exploring Identity in a Global Context*. London: Bloomsbury.
- Arab Canadian Lawyers Association. 2022. *Anti-Palestinian Racism: Naming, Framing and Manifestations* (Prepared by Dania Majid 4, 25, 2022). Available at: <https://www.canarablaw.org>.
- Bakan, Abigail B. and Yasmeeen Abu-Laban. 2021. "The Israel/Palestine Conflict and the Challenge of Anti-Racism: A Case Study of the United Nations World Conference Against Racism." *Ethnic and Racial Studies* 44 (12): 2167-2189.

International Court of Justice. 2024. "Application of the Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide in the Gaza Strip (South Africa v. Israel)", 26 January. <https://www.icj-cij.org/sites/default/files/case-related/192/192-20240126-ord-01-00-en.pdf>

Landy, David, Ronit Lentin and Connor McCarthy (eds). 2020. *Enforcing Silence: Academic Freedom, Palestine and the Criticism of Israel*. London: Zed Books.

Lynch, Marc and Shibley Telhami. 2023. "Scholars Who Study the Middle East are Afraid to Speak Out." *The Chronicle of Higher Education*, 5 December.

Mills, Charles. 1997. *The Racial Contract*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press.

Shaheen, Jack. 2001. *Reel Bad Arabs: How Hollywood Vilifies a People*. New York: Olive Branch Press.

Shaheen, Jack. 2008. *Guilty: Hollywood's Verdict on Arabs After 9/11*. Northampton: Olive Branch Press.

United Nations (Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights). 2023. "Speaking out on Gaza and Israel Must Be Allowed: UN Experts," 23 November. <https://www.ohchr.org/en/press-releases/2023/11/speaking-out-gaza-israel-must-be-allowed-un-experts>.